

INTERLINGUAL AND INTRALINGUAL ANALYSIS OF ESL LEARNERS' TRANSLATIONS: ITS IMPLICATIONS TO ENGLISH LANGUAGE EDUCATION

Kirck Michael B. De Leon¹, John Arvin V. De Roxas²

¹ Senior High School Department, Gregorio T. Crespo Memorial High School, Cabiao, Nueva Ecija, Philippines

² Department of English and Humanities, College of Arts and Social Sciences, Central Luzon State University, Science City of Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11392755>

ABSTRACT

Language proficiency is crucial across all human endeavors, particularly within English Language Education. Yet, research indicates challenges among ESL learners in mastering English, often attributed to L1 or L2 interference. This mixed-method study investigates the interlingual and intralingual interference present in ESL learners' translation outputs, emphasizing implications for English Language Education in the Philippines. Employing purposive sampling, participants underwent translation tests. Utilizing Gass & Selinker's (2008) error analysis framework and Keshavarz's (2011) taxonomy, errors were identified and categorized. Quantitative analysis revealed 189 total errors, while qualitative data underscored L1 and L2 knowledge interference. Interference patterns were evident across various linguistic elements. Despite expectations to learn both Filipino and English, participants still lack proficiency. This highlights the imperative for more effective programs and interventions to bolster students' language skills in English Language Education in the Philippines.

Keywords: *English Language Education, Error analysis, Interlingual, Intralingual, Interference*

INTRODUCTION

The English language is a remarkably influential and widely spoken global language, with a diverse history and a rich tapestry of linguistic influences. It has evolved, expanded, and prevailed over centuries. It is an ever-evolving tool for human expression and interaction in our interconnected world because of its versatility and capacity to absorb and incorporate new words and expressions. As a result, it has influenced a variety of industries, including business, science, technology, and entertainment. According to Rao (2019), English serves the purpose as a common language and a global language in order to maintain international relationships. There is, therefore, an inevitable role played by the English language in science, technology, and business, especially in language education.

English holds an essential role in language education for several reasons. For students, being proficient in English offers a wide range of possibilities in terms of career, higher education, and interaction with the world. Students are also engaged in using the internet that uses this language which makes it vital for digital literacy. Additionally, learning English opens the door to appreciating a variety of cultures and literary works from nations that speak the language. Overall, English plays a key role in enabling students to thrive in a connected and globalized world.

In the Philippine context, as a response to the poor performance of students in the National Achievement Test across learning areas, the English language curriculum was developed (Barrot, 2019). The overarching goal of the K-to-12 English curriculum, or the Language Arts and Multiliteracies Curriculum (LAMC), is "to develop communicatively competent and multiliterate learners who are competitive in this global economy" (Department of Education, 2016, as cited in Barrot, 2019). In the new language curriculum, subjects are decongested to prevent students from being bombarded with learning competencies and standards. The present language curriculum is stretched to 12 years, making students cover fewer learning competencies for a year (Barrot, 2019). Also, advanced English subjects are now offered in the senior high school.

Despite the revisions of the curriculum, empirical studies show that Filipino ESL learners encounter challenges in using the English language. For instance, Leaño et al.'s (2019) study analyzed the difficulties of the indigenous students in terms of speaking English. The analysis revealed that indigenous learners have difficulties in articulating ideas. The participants had difficulties expressing their feelings on entities around using English. The speaking problems can be attributed to the limited exposure to the English language which caused weaker intellectual capacity in learning English. Also, their inadequacy in terms of vocabulary influences their capacity to understand the meaning of English words and expressions resulting in the inability to pronounce words.

Tanpoco et al. (2019) focused on the Filipino to English transfer errors in writing. Their study revealed that the respondents had only an average skill in grammar. In line with this, Langga & Alico (2020) revealed that students as having difficulties in mechanics and grammar-related topics. The results were supported by the study of Aranda (2022)

which emphasized the learning challenges in the new senior high school English curriculum. The study also showed that the students have weak foundations in grammar and sentence construction which affects their ability to comprehend, construct, write, and speak English.

The abovementioned studies generally revealed that Filipino learners are having difficulties in using the English language. The errors committed by the ESL learners can be attributed to the L1 and L2 interference.

Aziz, et al. (2019) stated that language interference is the effect of language learners' L1 on their production of the language they learn, or the learners' L1 influences their L2 production. This interference is called the interlingual interference. While interference can happen because of the influence of the L1 on the L2 production, it does not mean that the learners' own language is the only reason why they commit mistakes in the target language or TL (Pratiwi & Fauziati, 2015). Interference may occur when students lack proficiency in the target language, leading to challenges in its utilization. This is called intralingual interference. Errors in the target language cannot solely be attributed to interference from the student's native language. Students may also falter in the target language due to their limited proficiency and challenges in its usage. According to Pratiwi (2015), citing Richard (1974), intralingual interference is the term used to describe items produced by learners that do not accurately reflect the structure of their L1 but rather generalizations based on limited exposure to the target language. These interferences can be reflected in language aspects such as grammar and vocabulary.

The aforementioned circumstances prompted the researchers to conduct the study which examines and analyzes the interlingual and intralingual interference in the translations of ESL learners and identifies its implication to the Philippine Language Education.

As it enhances the understanding of language acquisition and development in multilingual individuals, the study of interlanguage and intralanguage interference is essential. The study of these interferences informs language educators and learners on common challenges in language learning, assisting in the creation of more efficient teaching methods. Additionally, people can learn more about the intricacies of language use and promote more inclusive and context-appropriate communication by looking at both types of interference, especially in varied and multicultural communities.

Research Questions

This study, "Interlingual and Intralingual Analysis of ESL Learners' Translations: Its Implication To English Language Education," investigated and analyzed the language interference in ESL learners' written translations.

Specifically, this aimed to answer the following questions:

1. How may the interlingual interference be described and categorized in terms of:
 - 1.1 transfer of morphological elements;
 - 1.2 transfer of grammatical elements; and
 - 1.3 transfer of lexico-semantic elements?

2. How may the intralingual interference be described and categorized in terms of:
 - 2.1 addition;
 - 2.2 omission;
 - 2.3 ignorance of rule restriction;
 - 2.4 overgeneralization; and
 - 2.5 false analogy?
 3. What are the implications of the results to English Language Education?
-

METHODOLOGY

Locale

The research was carried out at Gregorio T. Crespo Memorial High School (GTCMHS), situated on Lopez Jaena Street, Entabulado, Cabiao, Nueva Ecija. GTCMHS was founded during the 2016-2017 school year, a collaborative effort between the Entablado Parents Association, DepEd-Cabiao, and the Cabiao Local Government Unit. In 2019, the school commenced its Senior High School program, initially offering the Humanities and Social Science strand.

Participants and Sampling

The study focused on Grade 11 Humanities and Social Sciences (HumSS) students who had previously undergone pre-assessment. Grade 11 learners were chosen because they had prior experience with translation activities and the HumSS curriculum emphasizes writing. To ensure the sample represented the population accurately and to focus on specific characteristics relevant to the research problem, purposive sampling was employed. The criteria for participant selection included being a resident of Nueva Ecija, having Tagalog as their first language (L1) and English as their second language (L2), and being among the top ten students who made errors during the translation pre-test. This approach aimed to gather detailed insights from participants who met these criteria, despite its subjective nature, to address the research objectives effectively.

Data Gathering Procedure

This mixed-method study aimed to identify and describe the language interference that happens in the learners' translation outputs. Due to COVID-19 restrictions, face-to-face data collection was not feasible, so the researchers utilized Google Forms for data collection and ensured remote supervision via Google Meet. Informed consent was obtained from participants and relevant authorities. Initially, participants were chosen based on pre-test scores, with the ten lowest scorers selected. A translation test was administered, and errors were quantified using the taxonomy of Keshavarz (2011). The translated texts were then analyzed and described. The researchers employed investigator triangulation for validity and reliability. The study employed a sequential explanatory design, starting with quantitative data collection, followed by qualitative analysis to explain the findings.

Instrument

The researchers utilized translation tests, including a pre-test and the translation test proper, to gather the necessary data. The translation test used was adapted from the study of Langga & Alico (2020) and comprised three passages from the Filipino work text "Filipino sa Piling Larang (Akademik)." These passages were translated from Filipino to English. The translation test underwent content-related validation which involves experts in Filipino and English languages.

Data Analysis

This research utilized mixed-method analysis techniques for quantitative and qualitative data present in the translation output of ESL learners. Quantitative analysis focused on the number of translation errors present in the outputs. Frequency count and percentage were employed for quantification. Qualitative analysis, on the other hand, described the language interference of Keshavarz (2011). Furthermore, the error analysis framework of Gass & Selinker (2008) framework guided the qualitative analysis to achieve the research objectives, with qualitative data supporting the quantitative findings as per the research design.

Scope and Delimitation

This study aimed to analyze the translation errors made by ESL learners using the framework of Gass & Selinker (2008) and the language interference taxonomy of Keshavarz (2011). Therefore, this study involves the quantification of errors and their descriptions in relation to interlingual and intralingual interference. The interlingual errors included in this research were the transfer of morphological, grammatical, and lexico-semantic elements. Intralingual errors included addition, omission, ignorance of rule restriction, overgeneralization, and false analogy.

RESULTS

The tables presented below show the frequency count and percentage distribution of interlingual and intralingual interference observed in the translation outputs of ESL learners.

Table 1. Frequency Count and Percentage of Interlingual Interference

Interlingual Interference	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Transfer of Morphological Elements</i>	24	32.88
<i>Transfer of Grammatical Elements</i>	22	30.14
<i>Transfer of Lexico-semantic Elements</i>	27	36.99
Total	73	100%

Table 1 provides the breakdown of interlingual interference observed in the translation outputs of ESL learners. According to the data presented, the transfer of lexico-semantic elements was the most prevalent type of interlingual interference which constitutes 27 cases or 36.99% of the total observed occurrences. This was closely followed by the transfer of morphological elements, which accounted for 24 cases (32.88%). Transfer of grammatical elements represented the lowest occurrence, with 22 cases (30.14%).

Table 2. Frequency Count and Percentage of Intralingual Interference

Intralingual Interference	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Addition</i>	7	6.03
<i>Omission</i>	8	6.90
<i>Ignorance of Rule Restriction</i>	91	78.45
<i>Overgeneralization</i>	6	5.17
<i>False Analogy</i>	4	3.45
Total	116	100%

Table 2 shows the classification of intralingual interference present in the outputs of the participants. The data reveals that ignorance of rule restriction emerged as the predominant type of intralingual interference which accounts for 91 cases or 78.45% of the total. This suggests that ESL learners frequently encounter difficulties in applying language rules correctly, leading to deviations from standard usage. Additionally, the table indicates that omission and addition errors were relatively common, with 8 cases (6.90%) and 7 cases (6.03%), respectively. Overgeneralization and false analogy, though less frequent, still contributed to the case of intralingual interference, with cases (5.17%) and 4 cases (3.45%), respectively.

DISCUSSION

This discussion includes the analysis of interference. The researchers used samples of faulty translations and other errors to provide clearer illustrations and representation for each of the interference. The discussion below utilized the codes ST which stands for *Source Text* and Pa which means *Participants*. Furthermore, the number indicates the number assigned to the participant (e.g. Pa 1 means Participant 1).

Interlingual Errors

Interlingual errors, or cross-linguistic interference, happen when "habits such as patterns or rules obstruct learners' ability to master the target language's forms and rules" (Cocjin, 2021). In this study, the researchers found negative transfers of morphological, grammatical, and lexico-semantic elements. Representations of each interlingual error are given in the following sections.

Transfer of morphological element

Errors in transferring morphological elements happen when the translator fails to apply the morphological features of the TL.

- ST: *“Ang proseso ay walang ipinagkaiba sa pagkabuo ng kambal na natural na nangyayari sa kaso ng identical twins.”*
- Pa1. *“The process is nothing distinguished in the formation of twins that natural occurring in the case of identical twins.”*

In the English language, one of the purposes why -ing is put at the end of a verb is to denote that the action is continuous. This could be the reason why there is an error in terms of translating Filipino verbs into English. In the sample above, the participant mistakenly translated the phrase “natural na nangyayari” to “naturally occurring”. It shows that the participant failed to consider the words that surround the word “nangyayari”. As a result, the participant directly translated the word “nangyayari” to “occurring” without considering that the word before it is an adverb, “natural” (“natural”). Furthermore, the suggested translation for the phrase is “naturally happens”. Therefore, the participant should have used “naturally occurs.”

- ST: *“...ang mga cell na bumubuo ng isang murang embrion...”*
- Pa7. *“... the cells that creating an young embryo...”*

- ST: *“Ang proseso ay walang ipinagkaiba sa pagkabuo ng kambal na natural na nagyayari sa kaso ng identical twins.”*
- Pa1. *“The process is nothing distinguished in the formation of twins that naturally occurring in the case of identical twins.”*

Also, in the phrase, “the cells that creating an young embryo...”, the word “bumubuo” was mistakenly translated to “creating”. The participant directly translated the word without considering the word preceded by the word “bumubuo” which is “that”. In English grammar, using verb-ing is incorrect when it is preceded by “that”.

In the first sample, it was revealed that L1 interference in terms of grammatical elements was also present. Interference like the sample above was discussed in the succeeding section.

The use of -ing in the translated verbs “occurring” and “creating” is unnecessary for they come after “naturally” and “that” respectively which do not require such forms.

ST: *“Ang mga tuklas na ito ang nagbunsod sa iba’t ibang modipikasyon at pagbabago sa teknolohiya ng komunikasyon.”*

Pa7. *“This discovery lead to different modification and change in communication technology.”*

Forming the past tense in the Filipino language is different from forming verbs in the English language where there is a need to consider if the verb is a regular or irregular verb. The TT reveals transfer errors in terms of forming the past tense of verbs using the TL. The participant failed to translate correctly the verb “nagbunsod” (led). In the Filipino language, the morpheme “-nag” signifies that the verb is in past tense. However, the participant used “lead” which is in the base form.

The negative transfers mentioned are more on the formation of verbs. Also, Akande (2003) discovered that students exhibit inadequate proficiency in utilizing English past participles, possessives, past tense, and plural inflectional morphemes. Moreover, in the analysis of Zaid, et. al (2017), it revealed that participants tend to use simple present tense in describing past events. Furthermore, the study, revealed that tenses were a major problem in students' writing. This error occurred due to limitations in the Malay language's grammar, which does not permit users to express specific time events, as noted by Zaid et al. (2017). This rule was brought within the L2 by the learners.

ST: *“Batay sa kasalukuyang kaalaman, may dalawang paraan ng pag-clone ng mga mammal.”*

Pa6. *“According to current study,there are two way of cloning a mammal.”*

The analysis also revealed that errors in pluralization are also present in the transfer of morphological elements. It can be seen in the statement, “According to current study,there are two way of cloning a mammal.”. In this case, the phrase “dalawang paraan” was translated to “two way”. The participant did not consider that there was a quantifier before the noun. The rule in the English morphological system, when a noun is preceded by a plural quantifier, it should take its plural form. However, the phrase “dalawang paraan” was mistakenly translated into “two way”, instead of “two ways”.

Similarly, Khatter (2019) found out that Arabic learners commit errors in pluralization when used with a quantifier such as “I have three sister.” This error happens because speakers tend not to pronounce the plural -s morpheme (Khatter, 2019).

Transfer of grammatical elements

Negative transfers of grammatical elements were also seen in the analysis. The sample below shows that the participant used word-by-word translation without considering the grammatical structure of the TL. As a result, the TT became erroneous in terms of sentence construction and word ordering.

ST: *“Ang proseso ay walang ipinagkaiba...”*
Pa1. *“The process is nothing distinguished...”*

Cuc (2017) revealed that word order errors were also present in the translation of Vietnamese using English. The phrase “một cô gái đẹp ” ("a beautiful girl") was translated to "a girl beautiful". In Vietnamese, adjectives come after nouns. On the other hand, in English, a noun is preceded by an adjective. The rule of the SL is different from that of the TL. Therefore, because of the participant's ignorance of the structure of the TL and word-by-word translation, words in the sentences were misordered.

Transfer of Lexico-semantic Elements

The analysis also shows that participants committed errors in terms of the transfer of lexico-semantic elements.

ST: *“...may dalawang paraan ng pag-clone ng mga mammal..”*
Pa4. *“There have two ways to close of those mammals.”*
ST: *“...makapaglagay ng unang satellite sa kalawakan.”*
Pa10. *“...that way the satellite are born in the universe”*
ST: *“Ang unang pamamaraan ay maituturing na artipisyal na pagkakambal.”*
Pa5. *“The first you can be considered artificial communicating.”*

The samples above show that the participants gave different equivalents to certain words. The participants used the words “close”, “born”, and “communicating” as translations of the words “pag-clone”, “makapaglagay”, and “pagkakambal” respectively. It can be seen that the participants used another word that, somehow, relates to the original words. In the analysis of Rajab, et. al. (2016), it revealed that words that do not relate to the original word were used to translate the ST. In their study, the words "follow" and "join" were used to substitute "imitate" and "monitor", respectively. In these sentences, the learner failed to convey the intended meaning of the ST.

ST: *“Sa sistemang ito, ang mga cell na bumubuo ng isang murang embrion ay pinaghihiwalay upang maging dalawa o higit pang indibidwal.”*
Pa1. *“In this system, the cells that form a cheap the embryo is separated in order be two or more individuals.”*

In the sample above, the participant used the word "cheap" (not expensive) as the translation of the word "mura" (young). It shows that the participant used a word that is synonymous with the original word but inappropriate in the context of the sentence. In the

study of Rajab, et. al. (2016), a similar case was seen. In the phrase, "who are very busy in their works", the participant mistakenly used the word "works" instead of "jobs" which is equivalent to the word "amail" in Arabic.

The analysis of interlingual interference revealed that participants commit errors in the transfer of morphological elements (i.e. pluralization, verb tenses, verb, and adverb structures), grammatical elements (i.e. word order, and word-by-word translation), and lexico-semantic elements (i.e. rendition of lexical items).

Intralingual errors

Intralingual errors are caused by interference within the TL itself. According to Keshavarz (2011), this error is the influence of one TL item upon another. This study reveals that intralingual errors such as addition, omission, ignorance of rule restriction, overgeneralization, and false analogy are present in the participant's output. Representation of each intralingual error is given in the following sections.

Addition

Angguni (2020) defines addition as the inclusion of unnecessary or incorrect elements in speech. In this study, it happened because the participants added unimportant items in the sentences that should not be present in a well-constructed sentence.

- Pa6. *"In the year 1960 when the first balloon telecommunication satellite we had."*
- Pa7. *"If fertilization occurs, the scientist that will create technological intervention to make clones of the created embryo."*
- Pa10. *"The telecommunications revolution are that have a big impact in technology in communication..."*

In the samples above, it can be seen that connecting words "when" and "that" are added in the sentences which are not necessary. In addition, adding such words greatly changes, if not distorts, the meaning and the structure of the sentences. The result revealed that the participants of this study committed addition of conjunction. Likewise, the study of Arabi & Ali (2014) revealed that the participants committed addition errors of conjunction. In fact, the addition of conjunctions had the highest percentage of errors in the study. Furthermore, in the analysis of Iranian EFL learners' errors in their written production, Ahmadvand (2008), as cited in Heydari & Bagheri (2012), found out that additions are one of the three frequently committed errors in terms of intralingual errors.

Omission

Omission stands in contrast to addition, occurring when students fail to include an essential element required for a properly constructed utterance. Samples such as this error are shown below.

Pa3. *"It was 1960 when a telecommunication satellite was a balloon."*

Pa5. *"...the fertilization must first take as a result of the union of the semen and egg."*

The first sample reveals that the participant only described telecommunication satellite as a balloon and not as a "created." Furthermore, the word "balloon" should not be used as a modifier but used as a type of telecommunication satellite, a balloon telecommunication satellite. The correct sentence construction for the sample above should be "It was in 1960 when a balloon telecommunication satellite was created." The same case happened in the second sample. In the sample, the participant used "take", instead of "takes place" to state that fertilization happened. These two samples revealed that the participants tend to omit the verb to complete a sentence.

The study of Walasari, et al (2021), shows that omission happened to have the highest percentage of errors. In the analysis, where omission had the highest percentage of errors, it was found that learners omitted essential specific items in their writing like verbs and auxiliaries, and prepositions. An example of omission errors found is "He fat" where the verb to be is omitted.

Ignorance of rule restriction

Ignorance of rule restriction occurs when there is a failure to observe the restrictions or existing structures (Sijono & Aristo, 2019). Moreover, this error happens when the L2 learners do not obey the structure of the target language. Below are samples of such errors committed in this analysis.

Pa9. *"... since they introduce telegraph past forty decades of 19th century."*

Pa7. *"In these process,..."*

"... the cells that creating an young embryo is..."

The sample revealed that the participant used the present tense of the verb "introduce". In the sample, since the telegraph was introduced in the 19th century, the verb should be in its past tense which is "introduced". This reveals that the participant has an ignorance in the usage of the tense of the verb.

Similarly, in the study of Situmorang (2024), it was found that participants also committed errors in terms of using the simple past tense. For instance, in the sentence "He is at home last day", the participant failed to distinguish among tenses. The phrase "last day" was not recognized as a visible signal that indicates that the action happened in the past. Therefore, the sentence should have used "was" instead of "is."

It is shown also in the sample that learners also have an ignorance in the usage of the demonstrative "these". In English grammar, the demonstrative "these" precedes a plural noun. However, the participant used these before the word "process" which is a

singular noun. This reveals that the participant was confused about the usage of singular or plural forms.

Atikah et al. (2022) also found that participants tend to commit errors in terms of singularizing or pluralizing nouns. There was an absence of plural markers of nouns and verbs. An example in the study mentioned "...has already been used ...by many teacher in the world. " showed the error caused by the ignorance of rule restrictions of the grammatical rule in the agreement of singular and plural nouns.

The last sample above shows the incorrect use of the verb to be. The participant had an error when the word "is" is used that refers to the word "cells", a plural noun, instead of "are." In the study of Sari (2019), one of the errors under ignorance of rule restriction happened in using the verb to be. In the sentence, "There is so many books", the error happened when the participant mistakenly used "is" with the noun "books", instead of using "are."

Overgeneralization

Overgeneralization happens when a participant overuses a certain grammatical rule or item. In this analysis, cases of overgeneralization were seen in the participants' outputs.

- Pa1 "...a cheap the embryo."
- Pa2 "The first one procedure..."
- Pa4 "The one way..."

Normally, an article is placed before the noun it refers to. However, in the analysis, it was found that the use of articles is being overgeneralized by the participants. In the first sample, the articles "a" and "the" are used even though they do not need to be used at the same time. Also, in the second sample and the third sample, "the" is used even though there is the word "one" that refers to the words "way" and "procedure."

Overusing of using the article "the" also happened in the analysis of Ouertani (2013) where the participants extended the use of 'the' to contexts where it is not needed. Furthermore, Ouertani (2013) pointed out that "this error has a developmental cause as it is due to overgeneralization."

False Analogy

False analogy is an error made by writers who do not fully understand a distinction in the target language. The authors make the error of assuming the L2 rules are based on their existing knowledge about a certain rule. Samples of false analogies committed by the participants in this analysis are as follows:

- Pa5. "childs"
- Pa9 "childrens"

The false analogy was seen in the case of pluralization errors as shown above. Regular nouns require only the addition of -s or -es to form their plural form. In the case of irregular nouns, the spelling is changed. However, participants applied the rule used for regular nouns to pluralize an irregular noun. Likewise, Kaweera (2013) discovered that L2 learners erroneously inferred pluralization rules in L2 based on their existing knowledge. As illustrated in Kaweera's (2013) examples, participants applied the pattern of adding 's' to form plurals, leading to errors such as 'gooses' and 'childs', if appending 's' automatically pluralizes these nouns.

- A. *My father used to feed many gooses in the back of the house.*
- B. *Childs in the village like to play with me.*

Intralingual errors, arising from within the target language, were observed in ESL learners' translations, encompassing addition, omission, rule restriction ignorance, overgeneralization, and false analogy. These errors, exemplified in the participants' outputs, underscore the challenges learners encounter in mastering the complexities of the target language.

Implications of the Findings of the Study to the English Language Education

This study identified, categorized, analyzed, and explained the interlingual and intralingual interference present in the ESL learners' translation output to identify possible implications to English Language Education.

The following implications from this study may be beneficial in improving Philippine Language Education:

1. Enhanced programs and interventions are necessary to address and enhance students' language skills effectively.
2. English textbooks and educational resources should integrate diverse activities, thorough exercises, and authentic evaluations centered on applying English language rules to enhance performance.
3. Collaboration between schools and communities is essential to organize activities aimed at enhancing learners' language mastery and proficiency.
4. It is imperative to develop and reinforce materials, including textbooks and interventions, that offer comprehensive discussions and assessments of English language usage, as well as appropriate word selection.
5. Reevaluation of the curriculum is needed to ensure students achieve full proficiency in language competencies, with a particular emphasis on grammar and composition.
6. Teachers require additional training to refine their teaching methods and strategies, thereby ensuring and enriching students' learning experiences.

Conclusions

Based on the analysis, the researchers concluded that:

1. Interlingual errors, stemming from cross-linguistic interference, were evident in the translation outputs of ESL learners, manifesting as negative transfers of morphological, grammatical, and lexico-semantic elements. These errors included inaccuracies in translating verb tenses, pluralization, word order, and lexical choices, reflecting challenges in applying the rules and structures of the target language.
2. These errors, stemming from within the target language itself, encompass various phenomena such as addition, omission, ignorance of rule restrictions, overgeneralization, and false analogy. Through examples provided in the analysis, it becomes evident that these errors can significantly impact the clarity and accuracy of learners' language output.
3. This study also provides valuable insights into the interlingual and intralingual interference observed in ESL learners' translation output and offers implications for enhancing English Language Education in the Philippines. Firstly, there is a clear need for enhanced programs and interventions tailored to address and improve students' language skills effectively. Secondly, English textbooks and educational resources should be enriched with diverse activities and authentic evaluations focused on applying English language rules to enhance performance. Thirdly, collaboration between schools and communities is crucial for organizing activities aimed at enhancing learners' language mastery and proficiency. Additionally, developing and reinforcing materials, including textbooks and interventions, that offer comprehensive discussions and assessments of English language usage and appropriate word selection is imperative. Furthermore, a reevaluation of the curriculum is necessary to ensure students achieve full proficiency in language competencies, with a particular emphasis on grammar and composition. Finally, teachers require additional training to refine their teaching methods and strategies, thereby ensuring and enriching students' learning experiences in English Language Education. These implications collectively contribute to the improvement of language education standards and the overall proficiency of ESL learners in the Philippines.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study on interlingual and intralingual interference in ESL learners' translation output, the following researchers recommended the following:

1. Comparative analyses between ESL learners and speakers of diverse languages can elucidate universal versus language-specific challenges in translation and language acquisition. By comparing learners from different linguistic backgrounds, researchers can identify the distinctive features of English and adapt teaching methods accordingly.
2. Research investigating the efficacy of pedagogical interventions in addressing interlingual interference can offer valuable insights for language educators. By testing diverse teaching methods and materials tailored to specific interference types, educators

can better support learners in overcoming language challenges and improving proficiency.

3. Enhanced programs and interventions tailored to students' needs are necessary, along with enriched textbooks and resources focusing on applying language rules effectively. Collaboration between schools and communities is vital for organizing activities to enhance language proficiency, alongside curriculum re-evaluation and teacher training to refine teaching methods and enrich learning experiences.

4. Future research in English as a Second Language (ESL) learning should explore specific types of interlingual interference, including morphological transfer, grammatical transfer, and lexico-semantic transfer, observed in ESL learners. By examining each type separately, researchers can gain a more nuanced understanding of the difficulties learners encounter in mastering these linguistic aspects.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers hereby declare our full compliance with ethical guidelines throughout the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all participants which ensured that they were fully aware of the study's objectives, procedures, and potential outcomes before agreeing to take part. Participants were also assured of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence. Anonymity was maintained to protect the identities of all respondents to safeguard their privacy and confidentiality. Measures were implemented to ensure the well-being of participants throughout the study.

The researchers also affirm that no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of this research, and every effort was made to avoid plagiarism in all aspects of the study. There was no bias in the interpretation of the findings, and the results were utilized solely for research purposes, with the intention of contributing to the body of knowledge in the field.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank the reviewers and editors of this paper. Earnest gratitude is extended to Mrs. Mary Ann M. Rodriguez, PhD, the students of GTCMHS, the authors' families and parents.

REFERENCES

- Ahmadvand, M. (2008). Analyzing errors of Iranian EFL learners in their written productions. Retrieved March 10, 2023, from <http://moslem17.googlepapers.com/AnalysingerrorsofIranianEFLlearners.pdf>
- Angguni, R. (2020). Interlingual and intralingual errors of writing descriptive text made by third semester students of English Education Department Sarjanawiyata Tamansiswa university Yogyakarta. *JELLT (Journal of English Language and Language Teaching)*, 4(2), 75-85.
- Akande, A. T. (2003). Acquisition of the inflectional morphemes by Nigeria learners of English language. *Nordic Journal of African Studies*, 12(3), 17-17.
- Arabi, H. & Ali, N. (2014). Explication of Conjunction Errors in A Corpus of Written Discourse by Sudanese English Majors. *Arab World English Journal*, 5(4): 111-130
- Aranda, M. R. R. (2022). Learning Challenges in the New Senior High School English Curriculum in the Philippines. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 21(11), 315-333.
- Atikah, D., Takulani, A. H., Astuti, D., & Sari, P. (2022). Examining Frequent Grammatical Errors in Student Theses: A Case Study of a Private University in Sulawesi. *KnE Social Sciences*, 91-109.
- Aziz, Z. A., Daud, B., & Yunidar, S. (2019). Second Language Interference towards First Language Use of Japanese Learners. *Indonesian Journal of English Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics*, 4(1), 159-176.
- Barrot, J. S. (2019). English curriculum reform in the Philippines: Issues and challenges from a 21st century learning perspective. *Journal of Language, Identity & Education*, 18(3), 145-160.
- Cocjin, A. L. (2021). Error analysis in the written texts of pre-service teachers. *Asian Journal of Research in Education and Social Sciences*, 3(4), 17-27.
- Gass, S.M. and Selinker, L. (2008). *Second Language Acquisition: An Introductory Course*. New York: Routledge Taylor and Francis Group.
- Heydari, P., & Bagheri, M. S. (2012). Error analysis: Sources of L2 learners' errors. *Theory and practice in language studies*, 2(8), 1583-1589.
- Keshavarz, M.H (2012). *Contrastive Analysis and Error Analysis*. Rahnama Publication 117-128
- Khatter, S. (2019). An Analysis of the Most Common Essay Writing Errors among EFL Saudi Female Learners. *Arab World English Journal*, 10(3): 364-381. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol10no3.26>
- Leaño, A. J., Rabi, N. M., & Piragasam, G. A. G. (2019). Speaking difficulties of Philippine indigenous learners in English Phonology. *International Journal Academic Research Business and Social Sciences*, 9(1), 1231-1244.
- Langga, P.M & Alico, J.C (2020). Students' Proficiency and Challenges in Filipino-to English Translation: The Case of Filipino Senior High School Students in a Private Institution. *International Journal of Linguistics, Literature and Translation*. DOI: 10.32996/ijllt

- Ouertani, Y. (2013). Errors in the use of English articles among 1st and 4th year EFL students at the higher institute of languages of Tunis (ISLT). *Journal of Teaching and Education*, 2(4), 353-363.
- Pratiwi, A. P., & Fauziati, E. (2015). Interlingual And Intralingual Errors of Writing Narrative Text Made By Junior High School And Senior High School Students (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta).
- Rao, P. S. (2019). The importance of English in the modern era. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR)*, 8(1), 7-19.
- Rajab, A. et al (2016). An investigation of Semantic Interlingual Errors in the Writing of Libyan English as Foreign Language Learners. *Arab World English Journal*, 7(4): 277- 296 DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol7no4.18>
- Sari, N., Mu'in, F., & Yamin, M. (2019). An analysis of intralingual grammatical errors made EFL students. *Lingua Educatia*, 1(2), 138-150.
- Sijono & Aristo T. (2019). An Analysis on Students' Erroneous Sentence Found in Descriptive Text. *Voices of English Language Education Society*, 3(2), 118-126. DOI: 10.29408/veles.v3i2.1560.g928
- Situmorang, K., & Pramusita, S. M. (2024). Errors Analysis in Using Simple Past Tense in Nursing Students' Writing Assignments. *ETERNAL (English Teaching Journal)*, 15(1), 144-155.
- Tanpoco, M., Rillo, R., & Alieto, E. (2019). Filipino to English transfer errors in writing among college students: Implications for the senior high school English curriculum. *Asian EFL*, 26(6.1), 227-246.
- Walasari, D., et al (2021). The Analysis Of Grammar Error In Writing Descriptive Text For Seventh Graders. *National English Education, Language, and Literature Seminar*. 39-45
- Zaid, S. B., Rashid, R. A., Azmi, N. J., & Yusri, S. S. (2017). Factors Affecting the Morphological Errors in Young ESL Learners' Writing. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 6(3), 129-136.